

EVALUATING THE IMPACT AND CHALLENGES OF THE PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA (PMFBY) IN JALNA DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA.

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Abstract

The present study evaluates the growth trajectory of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from 2016-17 to 2022-23, emphasizing its impact on income stability among insured farmers and identifying key implementation challenges in the Jalna district of Maharashtra. Employing the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), descriptive statistics, and Garrett ranking technique, the research provides a nuanced view of PMFBY's efficacy. The study was conducted across four talukas (Ambad, Ghansavangi, Jalna, and Bhokardan) in Jalna district, surveying 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers from 12 villages. The findings revealed mixed growth trends, with a national decline in insured farmers (CAGR of -7% in kharif and -2% in rabi seasons) while Maharashtra showed positive growth in the kharif season (CAGR of 20%), reflecting effective implementation in specific areas. Conversely, Jalna district recorded slight kharif growth but a -10% decline in rabi. Analysis of claims data highlighted an increase in reported claims yet a substantial decrease in approved and paid claims, notably in the rabi season, indicating administrative inefficiencies. Income stability analysis demonstrated that insured farmers experienced reduced income variability, shown by lower standard deviation and coefficient of variation, and a higher mean income compared to non-insured farmers. Major constraints included inadequate compensation, delays in disbursement, and a lack of expert crop loss assessments. The study concludes by recommending policy measures to boost farmer participation, address claims processing delays, and mitigate regional disparities in PMFBY's implementation, especially during the rabi season. These findings underscore PMFBY's role in stabilizing farmer income, while suggesting reforms to enhance program efficacy and farmer satisfaction.

Keywords: PMFBY, CAGR, Income stability, challenges

Introduction

Agriculture is vital to India's economy, employing 44 per cent of the population and contributing 18.3 per cent to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, farmers face numerous risks, including natural disasters, pests, diseases, and unpredictable climate conditions, leading to significant crop losses and destabilizing the sector. Effective risk management is crucial to protecting farmers' incomes and ensuring sector stability. Crop insurance has become essential for managing these risks. By pooling risks across many policyholders, it distributes the financial burden of crop losses, helping farmers recover from disasters. Insurance companies collect premiums, creating a fund used to compensate those affected. This risk distribution operates both spatially and temporally.

The Indian government has long recognized the importance of crop insurance in supporting farmers. The first significant steps towards crop insurance were taken in 1920 when Mr. Chakravarti proposed a rain insurance scheme in Mysore state. Though this initiative was limited in scope, it laid the foundation for future efforts. In 1943, the Dewas Junior State introduced a compulsory crop insurance plan, but it wasn't until after India's independence that crop insurance gained substantial government attention.

The breakthrough came in 1972 with the introduction of India's first individual farm-based crop insurance scheme, specifically targeting H-4 cotton. This was a significant step, but real transformation came with the Pilot Crop Insurance Scheme (PCIS) in 1979. The PCIS introduced an area-based approach, covering various crops such as grains, millets, oilseeds, cotton, potatoes, and gram, and was managed by the General Insurance Corporation of India (GIC). This was followed by the Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS) in 1985, which sought to provide widespread coverage by sharing the responsibilities for premium and claims between the central and state governments.

In 1999, the CCIS was replaced by the National Agriculture Insurance Scheme (NAIS), marking a major shift in India's crop insurance framework. The NAIS aimed to mitigate the financial losses of farmers caused by natural calamities and restore their economic stability. It also used an area-based approach that focused on homogeneous regions where losses could be more accurately assessed. Over the years, the NAIS was modified and evolved into the Modified National

Agriculture Insurance Scheme (MNAIS), while additional schemes like the Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS) were introduced to further enhance coverage.

A landmark development in India's crop insurance landscape was the introduction of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in January government. PMFBY sought to address the limitations of earlier schemes by offering more comprehensive and affordable insurance coverage with simplified premium rates and streamlined processes. Operating under the principle of "One Nation, One Crop, One Premium," the scheme aimed to alleviate the financial distress faced by farmers due to crop losses caused by natural calamities, pests, and diseases.

The PMFBY scheme offers farmers premium rates of 2 per cent for kharif crops, 1.5 per cent for rabi crops, and 5 per cent for commercial and horticultural crops. It operates within a multi-agency framework involving central and state governments, insurance companies, financial institutions, and local bodies. The Department of Agriculture oversees its implementation, with state governments adapting it to regional needs. Banks and cooperatives handle premium collection and compensation disbursement. A key feature of PMFBY is its use of technology, including remote sensing, drones, and mobile apps, to improve crop assessments and speed up claim settlements. This reduces delays in compensation and allows on-account claims, enabling farmers to receive up to 25 per cent of the insured amount when adverse weather conditions impact sowing or yield.

Despite its advantages, PMFBY faces some challenges that affect its overall effectiveness. Moral hazard remains a concern, with some farmers potentially reducing their use of inputs like fertilizers and pesticides, knowing that they are insured against crop failure, which can lead to reduced productivity. Administrative issues, including delays in claim settlements and difficulties in enrolling small and marginal farmers, also persist. These challenges emphasize the need for continuous monitoring, feedback, and policy adjustments to enhance the scheme's implementation and ensure it effectively meets the needs of its beneficiaries.

The study provides key recommendations for improving PMFBY's implementation, including addressing administrative challenges, enhancing outreach, and refining technology use. These steps can

better stabilize farmers' incomes and promote sustainable agriculture. The findings also contribute valuable insights to the broader discussion on agricultural insurance in India, highlighting ways to support farmers' well-being and strengthen the agricultural sector's resilience. In conclusion, crop insurance is a critical component of India's agricultural risk management strategy. Schemes like PMFBY play an important role in protecting farmers from the financial impacts of natural disasters, thus ensuring income stability and promoting the sustainability of the agricultural sector. However, to achieve long-term success, continuous improvements in implementation, outreach, and policy are essential.

Aditya *et al.* (2018) studied crop insurance adoption and impact in India using survey data from 35,200 households across 4,529 villages. Adoption was low, with 4.8% participation in the kharif season and 3.17% in rabi. Insured farmers had higher debt (₹91,108), input costs (₹5,322), investment (₹1,01,811), and output value (₹7,553) than voluntary insurers. However, while insurance allowed farmers to take on more risk, it had inconclusive effects on their overall welfare.

Jamanal *et al.* (2019) studied crop insurance in Karnataka, sampling 240 respondents across 24 villages. Using Garrett's Ranking Technique, they found that delayed claim disbursement was the top issue (GS 73.53), followed by inadequate compensation (GS 61.51) and bias in loss assessments (GS 56.42). Farmers suggested that claims should be paid before the next season (GS 75.70), establishing a dedicated insurance cell at the local level (GS 66.40), and increasing training on crop insurance (GS 54.91).

Panigrahi *et al.* (2019) investigated the challenges rice growers in Bhadrak district, Odisha, face in subscribing to the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). Using purposive selection for the district and random sampling of 120 farmers, the study identified financial constraints as the most significant challenge, particularly high premium rates. Other key obstacles included lengthy credit procedures, inadequate compensation, low credit assessments, and a lack of minimum insurance levels. Operational issues, such as delays in compensation and insufficient involvement of cooperatives and insurance companies, compounded the difficulties. Additionally, farmers faced social challenges, including distrust in the system and complications during claim settlements.

Sharon *et al.* (2019) analyzed crop insurance growth in India and Andhra Pradesh using AIC data. For NAIS in India, growth rates were strong across insured farmers (10.43%), area (8.98%), and premiums (23.1%). WBCIS had even higher growth, particularly in area insured (50.48%) and premiums collected (58.67%). In Andhra Pradesh, NAIS showed modest growth in premiums but declines in area insured (-0.27%) and claims paid (-17.85%). WBCIS saw high growth across all metrics, with the area insured rising by 232.83%.

Kumara and Kumari (2020) assessed the performance of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) relative to the Restructured Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (RWBCIS) from 2016-17 to 2018-19. Using ANOVA and Multiple Least Significant Difference (LSD) tests, they identified significant differences in farmers' premiums, gross premiums, claims reported, and claims paid for both schemes. Growth rate analysis revealed negative growth in the number of farmers and area insured under PMFBY (-1.04% and -4.86%, respectively), while RWBCIS exhibited positive growth (1.47% for farmers and 8.22% for area). The findings also indicated significant differences in farmers' premiums and gross premiums, suggesting greater benefits for insurance companies under PMFBY.

Kumar (2020) investigated the impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Raipur district, Chhattisgarh, and found a (5.42%) increase in the number of insured farmers from kharif 2016 to kharif 2018. During this period, the total insured sum rose from ₹290.09 crores in kharif 2016-17 to ₹371.74 crores in kharif 2018-19. Many farmers with crop insurance expressed appreciation for PMFBY, attributing their successful outcomes to the program. The study indicated that insured farmers experienced higher yields and profits compared to those without insurance.

Chadha and Srivastava (2022) analyzed growth in India's NAIS and WBCIS crop insurance schemes, finding consistent growth across metrics. NAIS showed the highest growth (10.60%) and instability (79.62%) in claims paid, with CAGR in insured farmers (4.40%), area (3.81%), and premiums (9.50%). WBCIS reported significant growth in benefitted farmers (14.10%) and premiums collected (11.87%), with some metrics showing non-significant positive growth. The study also reviewed newer schemes PMFBY and RWBCIS.

Nagesh *et al.* (2022) surveyed 120 farmers in Srikakulam district, Andhra Pradesh, to assess their knowledge of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). With ten farmers randomly selected from each of twelve villages, results showed that 61.67% had medium knowledge of the scheme, 20% had low knowledge, and 18.33% had high knowledge. The study suggests that government and extension agencies should work to close these knowledge gaps and improve PMFBY's effectiveness, emphasizing the need for timely indemnification to maximize benefits.

Kait and Sheoran (2022) analyzed the progress of crop insurance schemes in Haryana, specifically focusing on the National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS) from 2004 to 2012. By rabi 2012-2013, about 6.36 lakh farmers were insured, covering 7.69 lakh hectares with a sum insured of ₹83,407.57 crore and claims paid amounting to ₹4,367.97 crore. In contrast, the initial figures in 2004 were significantly lower, with only 1.68 lakh farmers insured over 2.40 lakh hectares. The study also evaluated the performance of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from 2016 to 2021, revealing that the kharif season had a greater coverage area (3,28,824 hectares) compared to the rabi season (4,93,306 hectares) and that more farmers were insured during kharif. Overall, the study highlighted the positive performance of NAIS in Haryana.

Rawat and Zechariah (2022) conducted a study in Faridabad district (2021-2022) to assess the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) among 120 farmers, split evenly between insured and uninsured groups. Focusing on Ballabgarh and Tigaon blocks, they found only 18 of the 60 insured farmers were satisfied with PMFBY. Among uninsured farmers, a majority (56.67%) reported a lack of awareness as the main reason for non-participation, highlighting the need for better outreach efforts.

Jiragal *et al.* (2023) examined constraints and suggestions for PMFBY among 150 beneficiaries and 50 non-beneficiaries in Kolar, Karnataka. Beneficiaries cited delays in claim disbursement (12.67%), inadequate compensation (12%), and perceived bias in loss assessment (11.33%) as top issues. Suggestions included timely claim payments (14.67%), reduced premiums for horticultural crops (13.33%), and disbursing claims before the next season (12.67%). Other recommendations were establishing a PMFBY cell at the block level and increasing awareness through media and SMS (12.67%).

This article aims to assess the progress of (PMFBY) in Jalna district, focusing on its impact on farmers' income stability, the challenges encountered during its implementation, and recommendations for improvement.

Methodology

This study utilized a multistage purposive sampling technique to select the district, talukas, villages, and sample farmers. Jalna district was chosen due to its large number of insured farmers. Within Jalna, four talukas were selected (Ambad, Ghansavangi, Jalna, Bhokardan) based on PMFBY's progress, and three villages per taluka were chosen using similar criteria. From each village, 10 insured and 10 non-insured farmers were randomly selected, providing a total sample of 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers. Data collection was conducted through surveys using a pre-tested schedule for personal interviews. Primary data were gathered from these farmers for the 2023 kharif season, while secondary data on PMFBY progress from 2016-17 to 2022-23 were obtained from sources like India Stat and the PMFBY websites. The study of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) primarily relied on secondary data, gathered from sources such as Agriculture Insurance Company of India Limited reports and

government websites, to assess PMFBY's growth using CAGR. Key indicators, such as the number of insured farmers, total area insured, claims data, and beneficiaries, were analyzed for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23. The CAGR was estimated by using following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a \cdot b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated (Number of farmer insured / Area insured / Reported claim / Approved claim / Total claim paid / Total farmer benefitted)

t = Time variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the equation.

$$\text{CGR (r)} = [\text{Antilog (log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze income, including mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation (CV), and Income Stability Index. The Income Stability Index was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Income stability index} = 1 - \text{CV}$$

indicating income stability for both insured and non-insured farmers. The CV and income stability index allowed for a comparative analysis of income variation and stability between the two groups.

For identifying implementation weaknesses, Garrett's Ranking Technique was applied. Farmers ranked various challenges, and the

ranks were converted into scores using Garrett's Table. Convert the ranks into Garrett scores using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Position} = \left(\frac{R_{ij} - 0.5}{N_j} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} factor by the j^{th} individual

N_j = Number of factors ranked by the j^{th} individual

These scores were then averaged to identify the most significant issues affecting PMFBY implementation in Jalna district.

Results And Discussion

3.1 Progress of PMFBY

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) analysis revealed key insights into the trends of insured farmers, insured area, reported claim, approved claim, total claim paid and no. of farmer benefitted under crop insurance schemes during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers

Trends in farmers' participation in crop insurance schemes vary across India, Maharashtra, and Jalna district. Nationally, insured farmer numbers declined, with a negative CAGR of -7% per year in the *kharif* season and -2% in *rabi*, raising concerns about farmers' risk management. Maharashtra, however, saw a positive CAGR of 20% in *kharif* and 3% in *rabi*, reflecting better enrollment. Jalna district showed only slight growth in *kharif* (1% CAGR) but a significant *rabi* decline (-10% CAGR), indicating local challenges. These trends highlight mixed performances, with regions like Maharashtra faring better, while others need targeted efforts to boost participation. Similarly, Chanda and Srinivastav (2022) found positive growth under the Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS), contrasting with these results.

Table 1: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7% **
		t value	-1.98
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20%
		t value	2.98
3	Jalna	CAGR	1% **
		t value	0.34

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area Insured

Trends in insured area for *kharif* and *rabi* seasons show regional differences across India, Maharashtra, and Jalna district. Nationally, insured area grew modestly at a 1% CAGR for both seasons, suggesting slow but steady coverage expansion. Maharashtra showed strong *kharif* growth (19% CAGR) and a slower but positive *rabi* increase (4% CAGR), reflecting effective coverage efforts. In contrast,

Jalna district saw a decline, with a -1% CAGR in *kharif* and a sharper -13% in *rabi*, highlighting challenges in maintaining coverage. Maharashtra's growth contrasts with Jalna's decline, especially in *rabi*, pointing to the need for targeted support. Similarly, Rathore *et al.* (2011) found positive insured area growth, while this study shows mixed regional outcomes.

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area of insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	1% **
		t value	0.51
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19% **
		t value	1.34
3	Jalna	CAGR	-1% **
		t value	-0.16

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmers benefitted

The number of farmers benefitting from crop insurance schemes shows a concerning downward trend across India, Maharashtra, and Jalna district, especially during the *rabi* season. Nationally, the number of beneficiaries declined sharply, with a -6% CAGR in *kharif* and -19% in *rabi*, suggesting reduced scheme effectiveness due to lower uptake or delayed claims. In Maharashtra, *kharif* saw a slight increase (1%

CAGR), but *rabi* matched the national decline at -19%. Jalna district experienced even steeper declines, with -2% in *kharif* and -34% in *rabi*, indicating significant challenges in claim settlements. These trends underscore the need for policy interventions to boost farmer benefits, particularly during the *rabi* season. Conversely, Sheoran and Kait (2023) found positive growth in beneficiaries, contrasting with these mixed results.

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmer benefitted under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-6% **
		t value	-3.02
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	1% **
		t value	-1.99 **

		t value	0.11	-0.73
3	Jalna	CAGR	-2%**	-34%**
		t value	-0.08	-0.87

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported claims

An analysis of reported claims from 2016-17 to 2022-23 reveals distinct trends in India, Maharashtra, and Jalna district for kharif and rabi seasons. Nationally, reported claims grew moderately in kharif (8% CAGR) and surged in rabi (44% CAGR), likely due to increased crop losses or improved reporting. In Maharashtra, kharif claims declined significantly (-41% CAGR), suggesting reduced insurance participation or fewer crop damages, while rabi claims rose slightly

(1% CAGR). In Jalna, kharif claims increased (14% CAGR), indicating heightened awareness or crop challenges, while rabi claims dropped notably (-25% CAGR), possibly due to fewer adverse events or claims processing inefficiencies. These trends highlight the need for targeted strategies to enhance crop insurance uptake and claims reporting, as Kumara and Kumari (2020) also reported positive claims growth, contrasting with these mixed results.

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported Claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	8%
		t value	2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41%**
		t value	-1.52
3	Jalna	CAGR	14%**
		t value	0.61

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved claims

An analysis of approved claims from 2016-17 to 2022-23 shows significant regional and seasonal differences in crop insurance compensation. Nationally, approved claims declined sharply in both seasons, with a -60% CAGR in kharif and -26% in rabi, indicating possible administrative inefficiencies or stricter approval criteria. In Maharashtra, approved

claims for kharif also dropped significantly (-42% CAGR), while rabi claims showed slight improvement (3% CAGR), suggesting modest progress. In Jalna, kharif claims grew positively (13% CAGR), signaling better claims management, but rabi claims declined significantly (-26% CAGR). These trends highlight the need for policy reforms to streamline claims approval, ensuring prompt compensation for farmers.

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved Claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-60%**
		t value	-2.47
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42%**
		t value	-1.57
3	Jalna	CAGR	13%**
		t value	0.58

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid

Trends in claim disbursements under crop insurance schemes from 2016-17 to 2022-23 reveal notable patterns across India, Maharashtra, and Jalna district for both kharif and rabi seasons. Nationally, total claims paid declined in both seasons, with a moderate drop of -5% CAGR in kharif and a more significant -20% in rabi, suggesting reduced payouts due to stricter processing policies or fewer reported crop damages. In Maharashtra, kharif payments showed positive growth at a 7% CAGR, indicating improved disbursement processes,

while rabi payments declined significantly (-13% CAGR), reflecting challenges in claims disbursement. Jalna district also saw positive growth in kharif claims (10% CAGR), highlighting better claims management, but rabi payments sharply declined (-27% CAGR), pointing to issues in the settlement process. Overall, despite improvements during the kharif season, the significant declines in rabi underscore the need for policy interventions to enhance the efficiency of claim payments. This contrasts with findings from Sharon *et al.* (2019), who reported positive growth rates in claims paid.

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-5%**
		t value	-1.01
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7%**
		t value	0.83
3	Jalna	CAGR	10%**
		t value	0.43

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

The impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers

The table 7 presents key metrics for gross income comparisons between scenarios with and without compensation. The metrics include standard deviation, mean, coefficient of variation, and income stability index. These metrics provide insight into yield stability, average performance, and income efficiency

Gross income stability and income stability index of sample insured farmers

The analysis of gross income stability and the income stability index for insured farmers highlighted the benefits of compensation in stabilizing and enhancing agricultural income. Several key metrics, such as standard deviation, mean, coefficient of variation (CV), and

income stability index, were used to compare income scenarios with and without compensation.

The standard deviation reflects income variability. Incomes with compensation had a slightly lower standard deviation (₹47,004.79) compared to without compensation (₹48,331.79). This indicated that compensation helped reduce income fluctuations, resulting in more consistent income outcomes. Farmers experienced less volatility in their earnings when compensation was provided.

The mean gross income increased from ₹150,629.50 without compensation to ₹154,374.00 with compensation, a rise of ₹3,744.50. This suggests that compensation positively impacted overall productivity and helped farmers achieve higher average incomes.

The CV is a relative measure of income variability. The CV decreased from 0.32 without compensation to 0.30 with compensation. This indicated that income was more stable and aligned with the average

when compensation was included, further reinforcing the role of compensation in stabilizing income.

The income stability index, which measures the efficiency of income generation, increased from 0.68 without compensation to 0.70 with compensation. This positive change indicated that compensation improved income efficiency, allowing farmers to achieve better financial outcomes.

Overall, compensation schemes contributed to a reduction in income variability, increased average income, and improved income efficiency. The data demonstrated that compensation enhanced both the financial stability and productivity of farmers, leading to more predictable and favourable economic outcomes. By mitigating income fluctuations and boosting overall earnings, compensation played a crucial role in improving the economic well-being of insured farmers.

Table 7: Income stability index of sample insured farmers from year 2016-17 to 2022-23

Particulars	Gross income without compensation	Gross income with compensation
Standard Deviation	48331.79	47004.79
Mean	150629.5	154374
Coefficient of Covariation	0.32	0.30
Income Index	0.68	0.70

The analysis of income stability for insured farmers under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) indicated that compensation had a beneficial impact. With compensation, the standard deviation of gross yields was ₹47,004.79, slightly lower than ₹48,331.79 without compensation, suggesting reduced yield variability. The mean gross yield increased to ₹154,374.00 with compensation, compared to ₹150,629.50 without. The coefficient of variation (CV) was lower at 0.30 with compensation versus 0.32 without, indicating more consistent yields. Additionally, the income index rose from 0.68 without compensation to 0.70 with, reflecting improved efficiency in income generation.

The weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest its improvement

The table 8 presents the constraints in the adoption of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) as reported by 120 sampled insured farmers, ranked according to Garrett's ranking technique. The constraints are ranked based on their mean scores, which indicate the severity and importance of each issue from the farmers' perspective.

Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers

The most significant constraint was "Insufficient compensation under PMFBY," with a Garrett's mean score of 76.52, ranked first. Farmers felt the compensation provided was inadequate, which undermined trust in the scheme. This finding is consistent with studies such as [6] Jamanal *et al.* (2019), which similarly highlighted insufficient

compensation as a major shortcoming in agricultural insurance schemes. The second-highest constraint was "Delay in realization of compensation," with a mean score of 70.43, emphasizing the financial strain caused by slow compensation disbursement. This aligns with similar concerns identified in other studies regarding delays in agricultural insurance payments. Ranked third, "Experts are unavailable for assessment of crop loss" received a mean score of 60.31. This shortage of qualified assessors negatively impacts the accuracy of crop loss evaluation and claim processing. "Inadequate coordination between banks and farmers," ranked fourth with a score of 58.5, highlights communication barriers that hinder the smooth functioning of the scheme. Other key constraints included "Frequent changes in policy terms" (50.83) and "Late claim disbursement before the next season" (47.58), reflecting confusion and financial stress caused by delayed and inconsistent processes. Farmers also cited concerns about access to PMFBY portals (36.97), trust in the scheme (32.03). This finding is contrast to [7] Panigrahi *et al.* (2019), lack of assurance even after assessments (31.83), and corruption in claim settlement (22.77). This finding is similar to [8] Nagesh *et al.* (2022). Addressing these challenges, including improving compensation, ensuring timely payments, and reducing procedural delays, could enhance PMFBY's adoption and effectiveness. Strengthening communication, maintaining policy consistency, and mitigating corruption are essential for increasing trust and satisfaction among farmers.

Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers (N=120) by Garretts ranking

Sr. no.	Constraints	Garrett's Mean	Garrett's Rank
1	Insufficient coordination of banks and farmers	58.5	IV
2	Insufficient compensation under PMFBY	76.52	I
3	Delay in realization of compensation	70.43	II
4	corruption while assessment and settling claims	22.77	X
5	Frequent change in policy terms or condition create confusion while claim settlement	50.83	V
6	Experts are unavailable for assessment of crop loss	60.31	III
7	Claim should be dispersed before starting of next season	47.58	VI
8	Hard to trust the scheme due to past experience	32.03	VIII
9	Even after assessment by agency there is no assurance of compensation	31.83	IX
10	PMFBY Portals should be updated to access the claim details	36.97	VII

Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Insured farmers provided several suggestions to improve the implementation of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), with the top priorities centered around enhancing compensation and

streamlining the claims process. The most frequent suggestion, offered by 76 farmers (63.33 per cent), was the timely disbursement of compensation. This reflects the crucial need for quick financial support to help farmers recover and prepare for the next agricultural season. A close second, 64 farmers (53.33 per cent), advocated for increasing the adequacy of compensation, as many felt that the current amounts were insufficient to cover their losses. This aligns with findings by [8] Rawat and Zechariah (2022), who also ranked quick claim settlement as a top priority. Moreover, 61 farmers (50.83 per cent) emphasized the need for claims to be disbursed before the start of the next season to avoid delays in sowing and maintain continuity in production, this aligns with findings by [9] Jiragal *et al.* (2023). Transparency in the compensation process was highlighted by 48 farmers (40 per cent), who called for clearer communication and accountability from

insurance agencies. Other suggestions included offering price guarantees (46 farmers, 38.33 per cent) to manage market risks, and implementing a uniform indemnity policy across regions and crops (43 farmers, 35.83 per cent), to reduce confusion and inconsistencies. Improving agency operations was mentioned by 31 farmers (25.83 per cent), and expanding the coverage to include more crops was suggested by 39 farmers (32.5 per cent). Less frequently, farmers called for better information dissemination on compensation details (23 farmers, 19.17 per cent) and increased awareness of the scheme (22 farmers, 18.33 per cent). These suggestions highlight the need for better communication and understanding of the scheme. In summary, the primary concerns focus on timely and adequate compensation, transparency, and expanding the scheme's coverage.

Table 9 : Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Sr.no.	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Adequate Compensation	64	53.33	II
2	Timely Compensation	76	63.33	I
3	Transparency from Agencies	48	40.00	IV
4	Awareness of the Scheme	22	18.33	X
5	Complete Information on Compensation	23	19.17	IX
6	Improved Agency Operations	31	25.83	VIII
7	Uniform Indemnity for different regions and types of crops	43	35.83	VI
8	A greater number of crops are covered.	39	32.50	VII
9	Claims should be distributed before the start of the next season.	61	50.83	III
10	The insurance agency should offer insurance cover to include price guarantees.	46	38.33	V

Conclusion

The analysis of the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for key aspects of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from 2016-17 to 2022-23 reveals both positive trends and persistent challenges in the scheme's implementation. Nationally, there was a decline in the number of insured farmers during both *kharif*-7 per cent per annum and *rabi* -2 per cent per annum seasons, indicating a concerning disengagement from the scheme, which threatens farmers' financial security and risk management. However, Maharashtra showed promising progress during the *kharif* season with a positive CAGR of 20 per cent per annum, suggesting that targeted promotional efforts can improve participation. Despite this, the slower growth during the *rabi* season 3 per cent per annum in Maharashtra and the significant decline in Jalna district's *rabi* participation -10 per cent per annum highlight the need for region-specific interventions. The trends in insured area followed a similar pattern, with minimal national growth but better performance in Maharashtra, particularly during *kharif*. On the claims front, while national-level reporting improved, the drop in approved and paid claims especially during the *rabi* season points to administrative inefficiencies and barriers in the claims process. This calls for targeted efforts to streamline the claims process and improve awareness. Regarding income stability, compensation under PMFBY positively impacted farmers' financial outcomes. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation in gross income were lower with compensation, reflecting reduced income variability and better financial stability. Additionally, the mean gross income increased with compensation, indicating that farmers receiving compensation had higher average income levels. The income stability index also rose, signifying improved income efficiency, which highlights PMFBY's role in enhancing financial security and agricultural productivity. However, the study also identifies critical constraints in PMFBY's execution, such as insufficient compensation, delays in disbursement, and lack of experts for crop loss assessment. Farmers prioritized timely disbursement, adequate compensation, and transparency. Addressing these issues and implementing region-specific reforms is essential to enhance the scheme's effectiveness and foster trust among farmers.

To enhance the implementation of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), several policy implications are proposed. First, it is crucial to mandate timely disbursement of compensation, ensuring claims are settled before the onset of the next cropping season. The compensation formula should be revised to accurately reflect actual losses, with a minimum compensation guarantee introduced for small and marginal farmers. Additionally, insurance agencies must improve transparency by regularly updating farmers on claim statuses, compensation criteria, and payout timelines through SMS or digital platforms. Expanding PMFBY to include market risk coverage, such as a price guarantee mechanism, is essential to protect farmers from price fluctuations. Implementing a uniform indemnity policy will standardize compensation calculations and payouts across various regions and crops. Moreover, expanding the coverage of PMFBY to include more crops vital to farmers' livelihoods is recommended. Streamlining insurance agency operations through simplified and digitized claim submission processes can help reduce bureaucratic delays. Lastly, a comprehensive farmer education campaign should be launched to ensure that all insured farmers are well-informed about the scheme's coverage, compensation processes, and their rights.

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